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The Grand Canyon of the Colorado River - a super wonder of nature. Tourist, geographical and social expedition to Arizona, USA

Tomasz Borowski

The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin,
22, Mickiewicza Street, 78-520 Złocieniec, District Drawski, West Pomerania, Poland

E-mail address: tomasz.elvis.borowski@wp.pl

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the super beauty of the Colorado River Canyon and the social aspect in Arizona, USA. The illiteracy known in the world and existing in the USA on the example of Arizona is also presented in this paper. It is hard to agree that Americans are a smart nation. It can only be said that the society is now genetically different from Europe, etc. Widespread and pervasive illiteracy in the USA is a classic that is caused only by social policy in the USA. The expedition took place in May 2008.

Keywords: Arizona, Colorado River Canyon, tourism, geography, social aspect

INTRODUCTION

A tourist expedition to Arizona in the USA took place in May 2008. The beginning of the route began with a flight from the Okęcie airport in Warsaw (Poland), transit via New York to the city of Phoenix (the main city of Arizona, USA).

The views from the plane show the endless beauty of the sky and clouds (**Photos 1-8**).

Approaching the New York airport, you can immediately observe and admire the immensity and vastness of the NY city from the window of the plane (**Photos 9-18**). At the airport in New York (Photo 19). A rich and modern city but a clogged toilet at the airport must be an additional tourist attraction at the outset in NY (**Photo 20**).

In front of the airport in New York – heavy traffic (**Photos 21-26**). **Photos 27-29** show a flight from New York to Arizona's capital, Phoenix. **Photos 30 & 31** show the airport in Phoenix, AZ.

Photos 32 & 33 show a commemorative photo with an American soldier, next to the Phoenix airport. He has some military unit markings on his beret, it looks like a road sign on a beret. In the distance, on the right, in tinted glasses – a secret police officer.

Taxi stand at the airport – limousines like buses ... (**Photos 34 & 35**).

Photos 36-40 show the hotel next to the airport (\$50 per night).

The trip from Phoenix, AZ, to the Grand Canyon of the Colorado River took quite a long time, it was done by taxi. The price from the city of Phoenix to the Grand Canyons by taxi after negotiations was \$200. Fuel in the USA is cheap, so I was happy to drive with a smile to the Grand Canyon of the Colorado River from Phoenix observing the geology and nature of Arizona (**Photos 41-77**).

It is difficult for me to describe the beauty of the Canyon When I saw the geological beauty of the Canyon, I knelt down in front of the Canyon. I could not describe this geological wonder. I really could not do it. I was in shock I felt like I was on another planet. The Grand Canyon of the Colorado River is the natural history of the earth's geology – the entire Palaeozoic is at your fingertips (**Photos 78-112**).

After returning from the Canyon, I stayed at a hotel in the city of Tusayan (AZ), south of the Grand Canyon National Park. Price per night: \$100. In the hotel room, I turned on the TV and immediately saw the iconic Clint Eastwood ... (**Photo 113**).

In the evening I went to a regional restaurant in the city of Tusayan. There I ordered fries and some sliced fried meat. I sat at a table and waited for my meal. While waiting, I watched

the tourists' appearance and behaviour. Linguistic multiculturalism is noticeable almost all over the world.

I observed a very unpleasant phenomenon in this restaurant, namely: meals in the kitchen are prepared and served to tourists by indigenous people, i.e. Indians, and at the cash register, as always, there are Chinese. This is a very sad phenomenon – enslaved indigenous Indians work for the Chinese I felt weird and asked to pack a takeaway meal. I ate at the hotel. I could not eat and look at the slavish nature of this system.

The next day, I hitchhiked south from the city of Tusayan to Flagstaff, seeing and admiring the surrounding landscapes as I traveled.

Staying in the city of Flagstaff for the night, I had difficulty getting a hotel room. Most hotels have poor service. But I found one cheap hotel with nice staff for \$60. The city of Flagstaff is beautiful, quiet and clean (**Photos 114-128**). Climbing a small mountain, I admired the views and the endless, very long train with wagons (**Photos 116 & 117**). Often in the city you can see volcanic remnants in squares, parks and private gardens (**Photo 127**).

The return trip was from the city of Flagstaff to Phoenix by bus. Ticket price \$28. From the windows of the bus I admired the beauty of Arizona's landscapes. During a stop at a gas station, I spotted a classic beautiful red convertible Ford Mustang from Minnesota (**Photos 129-132**). There is not much traffic at the gas station surrounded by nice views (**Photos 133-142**). On the bus journey from Flagstaff to Phoenix, the majority of travellers are African American women. All obese, chubby, heavily fat. Bloated, conceited and full of pride. These are characteristics of African American women in Arizona, and certainly not only there.

After getting to the city of Phoenix by bus in the evening, I rented a hotel for \$50. The service in this hotel was not very nice, because the receptionist was an obese, heavily fat African American. But the hotel room was standard clean and well maintained for a city centre location (**Photos 159-169**).

In the morning, while exploring the city of Phoenix, I observed the beautiful, well-kept cactuses in various roadside squares that are common here (**Photos 143-152**). The city of Phoenix is a very clean, well-maintained and modern city (**Photos 143-194**). **Photos 173-179** show famous Harley Davidson motorcycles and me next to them in a roadside parking lot. I have to comment on an international hotel I stayed in but it was not “international” at all. Local Americans are usually uneducated and the world revolves only around their State.

I realised that for most Americans the globe is flat. And I believe that for most Americans, the earth is not flat, but concave. Illiteracy is evident at the hotel where I stayed. The pictures show the national flag of Germany next to the flags of Brazil and France. It is nothing extraordinary, but it is hanging upside down, which indicates a lack of knowledge of geography and world politics to describe it only briefly (**Photos 160-164**).

The city of Phoenix is generally deserted because at the time there was a game in the main stadium. A strange and incomprehensible event happened in one of the supermarkets in the city of Phoenix. I made a big purchase for several hundred dollars. The bill was \$800. I paid in cash. And the problem began. The African American woman at the counter could not count the money. She wanted a credit card which I did not have. I paid with 6 \$100 bills and gave the remaining \$200 in coins by changing the bills earlier at the bank (**Photos 191 & 192**).

The cashier could not count 25 cent coins to \$200. She had a lot of trouble. She called the bodyguard and the bodyguard said – “money is money ...”.

I said that in Poland such a lady at the cash register would only work at sweeping with a broom, but not in the store, but only outside. And on that confirming unkind touch, I ended my

trip to Arizona. The photo shows the car of the famous Chicago police at the airport during a stopover from Phoenix to Warsaw (Poland) (**Photo 195**).

CONCLUSIONS

The Grand Canyon of the Colorado River is tourism to another planet. The views and beauty cannot be put into words. The beauty of natural wonders is phenomenal. Additional attractions in local shops discourage tourism. There are white and black sides to traveling to this area.

References

- [1] Zican He, Zhaohua Sun, Weixing Zhou, Yitian Li, Yong Hu Gravel-Sand Transition of the Yangtze River: Human Disturbances, Migration Processes, and Controlling Factors, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface* 128, no. 66 (Jun 2023). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022JF006984>
- [2] Zican He, Zhaohua Sun, Yitian Li, Qianyi Zhao, Yong Hu, Zhenghao Chen Response of the gravel–sand transition in the Yangtze River to hydrological and sediment regime changes after upstream damming, *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 47, no. 22 (Nov 2021) 383–398. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.5254>
- [3] Laura V. Alvarez, Paul E. Grams An eddy-resolving numerical model to study turbulent flow, sediment and bed evolution using Detached Eddy Simulation in a lateral separation zone at the field-scale, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface* (Sep 2021). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JF006149>
- [4] Charles M. Shobe, Jens M. Turowski, Ron Nativ, Rachel C. Glade, Georgina L. Bennett, Benedetta Dini The role of infrequently mobile boulders in modulating landscape evolution and geomorphic hazards, *Earth-Science Reviews* 220 (Sep 2021): 103717. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2021.103717>
- [5] Erich R. Mueller, Paul E. Grams A Morphodynamic Model to Evaluate Long-Term Sandbar Rebuilding Using Controlled Floods in the Grand Canyon, *Geophysical Research Letters* 48, no. 99 (May 2021). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021GL093007>
- [6] David J. Topping, Paul E. Grams, Ronald E. Griffiths, David J. Dean, Scott A. Wright, Joel A. Unema Self-Limitation of Sand Storage in a Bedrock-Canyon River Arising From the Interaction of Flow and Grain Size, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface* 126, no.55 (May 2021). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020JF005565>
- [7] Charles M. Shobe, Georgina L. Bennett, Gregory E. Tucker, Kevin Roback, Scott R. Miller, Joshua J. Roering Boulders as a lithologic control on river and landscape response to tectonic forcing at the Mendocino triple junction, *GSA Bulletin* 133, no.3-43-4 (Jul 2020): 647–662. <https://doi.org/10.1130/B35385.1>
- [8] David J. Dean, David J. Topping, Paul E. Grams, Alexander E. Walker, John C. Schmidt Does Channel Narrowing by Floodplain Growth Necessarily Indicate Sediment

- Surplus? Lessons From Sediment Transport Analyses in the Green and Colorado Rivers, Canyonlands, Utah, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface* 125, no. 1111 (Oct 2020). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JF005414>
- [9] Paul E. Grams, Daniel Buscombe, David J. Topping, Matt Kaplinski, Joseph E. Hazel How many measurements are required to construct an accurate sand budget in a large river? Insights from analyses of signal and noise, *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 44, no.11 (Sep 2018): 160–178. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.4489>
- [10] Alan Kasprak, Joel B Sankey, Daniel Buscombe, Joshua Caster, Amy E East, Paul E Grams Quantifying and forecasting changes in the areal extent of river valley sediment in response to altered hydrology and land cover, *Progress in Physical Geography: Earth and Environment* 42, no.66 (Sep 2018): 739–764. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0309133318795846>
- [11] Daniel R. Hadley, Paul E. Grams, Matthew A. Kaplinski Quantifying geomorphic and vegetation change at sandbar campsites in response to flow regulation and controlled floods, Grand Canyon National Park, Arizona, *River Research and Applications* 34, no. 99 (Sep 2018): 1208–1218. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rra.3349>
- [12] David Milan, George Heritage, Stephen Tooth, Neil Entwistle Morphodynamics of bedrock-influenced dryland rivers during extreme floods: Insights from the Kruger National Park, South Africa, *GSA Bulletin* 130, no.11-1211-12 (May 2018): 1825–1841. <https://doi.org/10.1130/B31839.1>
- [13] David J. Topping, Erich R. Mueller, John C. Schmidt, Ronald E. Griffiths, David J. Dean, Paul E. Grams Long-Term Evolution of Sand Transport Through a River Network: Relative Influences of a Dam Versus Natural Changes in Grain Size From Sand Waves, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface* 123, no.88 (Aug 2018): 1879–1909. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2017JF004534>
- [14] Erich R. Mueller, Paul E. Grams, Joseph E. Hazel, John C. Schmidt Variability in eddy sandbar dynamics during two decades of controlled flooding of the Colorado River in the Grand Canyon, *Sedimentary Geology* 363 (Jan 2018): 181–199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sedgeo.2017.11.007>
- [15] Virginia Ruiz-Villanueva, Alexandre Badoux, Dieter Rickenmann, Martin Böckli, Salome Schläfli, Nicolas Steeb, Markus Stoffel, Christian Rickli Impacts of a large flood along a mountain river basin: the importance of channel widening and estimating the large wood budget in the upper Emme River (Switzerland), *Earth Surface Dynamics* 6, no.44 (Nov 2018): 1115–1137. <https://doi.org/10.5194/esurf-6-1115-2018>
- [16] Gemma Lobera, Ignacio Andrés-Domenech, José A. López-Tarazón, Pedro Millán-Romero, Francisco Vallés, Damià Vericat, Ramon J. Batalla Bed disturbance below dams: observations from two Mediterranean rivers, *Land Degradation & Development* 28, no.88 (Sep 2017): 2493–2512. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.2785>
- [17] Ronald E. Griffiths, David J. Topping Importance of measuring discharge and sediment transport in lesser tributaries when closing sediment budgets, *Geomorphology* 296 (Nov 2017): 59–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2017.08.037>

- [18] Barbara E. Ralston, Neil S. Cobb, Sandra L. Brantley, Jacob Higgins, Charles B. Yackulic Taxonomic and Compositional Differences of Ground-Dwelling Arthropods in Riparian Habitats in Glen Canyon, Arizona, USA, *Western North American Naturalist* 77, no.33 (Oct 2017): 369–384. <https://doi.org/10.3398/064.077.0309>
- [19] Ron B. Kegerries, Brandon C. Albrecht, Eliza I. Gilbert, W. Howard Brandenburg, Adam L. Barkalow, Mark C. McKinstry, Harrison E. Mohn, Brian D. Healy, James R. Stolberg, Emily C. Omana Smith, Clay B. Nelson, Ron J. Rogers Occurrence and Reproduction by Razorback Sucker (*Xyrauchen texanus*) in the Grand Canyon, Arizona, *The Southwestern Naturalist* 62, no.33 (Nov 2017): 227–232. <https://doi.org/10.1894/0038-4909-62.3.227>
- [20] Jean-Louis Grimaud, Chris Paola, Chris Ellis Competition between uplift and transverse sedimentation in an experimental delta, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface* 122, no.77 (Jul 2017): 1339–1354. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017JF004239>
- [21] Miles E. McCoy-Sulentic, Thomas E. Kolb, David M. Merritt, Emily C. Palmquist, Barbara E. Ralston, Daniel A. Sarr Variation in species-level plant functional traits over wetland indicator status categories, *Ecology and Evolution* 7, no.1111 (Apr 2017): 3732–3744. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.2975>
- [22] Miles E. McCoy-Sulentic, Thomas E. Kolb, David M. Merritt, Emily Palmquist, Barbara E. Ralston, Daniel A. Sarr, Patrick B. Shafroth Changes in Community-Level Riparian Plant Traits over Inundation Gradients, Colorado River, Grand Canyon, *Wetlands* 117 (Mar 2017). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13157-017-0895-3>
- [23] Karen J. Schlatter, Matthew R. Grabau, Patrick B. Shafroth, Francisco Zamora-Arroyo Integrating active restoration with environmental flows to improve native riparian tree establishment in the Colorado River Delta, *Ecological Engineering* (Mar 2017). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2017.02.015>
- [24] Laura V. Alvarez, Mark W. Schmeeckle, Paul E. Grams A detached eddy simulation model for the study of lateral separation zones along a large canyon-bound river, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface* 122, no.11 (Jan 2017): 25–49. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016JF003895>
- [25] Ana Casado, Jean-Luc Peiry, Alicia M. Campo Geomorphic and vegetation changes in a meandering dryland river regulated by a large dam, Sauce Grande River, Argentina, *Geomorphology* 268 (Sep 2016): 21–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2016.05.036>
- [26] Brian D. Collins, David R. Bedford, Skye C. Corbett, Collin Cronkite-Ratcliff, Helen C. Fairley Relations between rainfall-runoff-induced erosion and aeolian deposition at archaeological sites in a semi-arid dam-controlled river corridor, *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 41, no.77 (Jan 2016): 899–917. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.3874>
- [27] Massimo Rinaldi, William Amponsah, Marco Benvenuti, Marco Borga, Francesco Comiti, Ana Lucía, Lorenzo Marchi, Laura Nardi, Margherita Righini, Nicola Surian An integrated approach for investigating geomorphic response to extreme events: methodological framework and application to the October 2011 flood in the Magra

- River catchment, Italy, *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 41, no.66 (Feb 2016): 835–846. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.3902>
- [28] Alan D. Howard, Sylvain Breton, Jeffrey M. Moore Formation of gravel pavements during fluvial erosion as an explanation for persistence of ancient cratered terrain on Titan and Mars, *Icarus* 270 (May 2016): 100–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.icarus.2015.05.034>
- [29] Ryan S. Crow, Karl E. Karlstrom, William McIntosh, Lisa Peters, Laura Crossey, Athena Eyster A new model for Quaternary lava dams in Grand Canyon based on 40 Ar/ 39 Ar dating, basalt geochemistry, and field mapping, *Geosphere* 11, no.55 (Aug 2015): 1305–1342. <https://doi.org/10.1130/GES01128.1>
- [30] Joel B. Sankey, Barbara E. Ralston, Paul E. Grams, John C. Schmidt, Laura E. Cagney Riparian vegetation, Colorado River, and climate: Five decades of spatiotemporal dynamics in the Grand Canyon with river regulation, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Biogeosciences* 120, no.88 (Aug 2015): 1532–1547. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015JG002991>
- [31] Laura Nardi, Massimo Rinaldi Spatio-temporal patterns of channel changes in response to a major flood event: the case of the Magra River (central-northern Italy), *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 40, no.33 (Oct 2014): 326–339. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.3636>
- [32] D. Buscombe, P. E. Grams, M. A. Kaplinski Characterizing riverbed sediment using high-frequency acoustics: 2. Scattering signatures of Colorado River bed sediment in Marble and Grand Canyons, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface* 119, no. 1212 (Dec 2014): 2692–2710. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014JF003191>
- [33] Erich R. Mueller, Paul E. Grams, John C. Schmidt, Joseph E. Hazel, Jason S. Alexander, Matt Kaplinski The influence of controlled floods on fine sediment storage in debris fan-affected canyons of the Colorado River basin, *Geomorphology* 226 (Dec 2014): 65–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2014.07.029>
- [34] Joel L. Pederson, Gary R. O'Brien Patterns in the Landscape and Erosion of Cultural Sites Along the Colorado River Corridor in Grand Canyon, USA, *Geoarchaeology* 29, no.66 (Sep 2014): 431–447. <https://doi.org/10.1002/gea.21490>
- [35] Ryan Crow, Karl Karlstrom, Andrew Darling, Laura Crossey, Victor Polyak, Darryl Granger, Yemane Asmerom, Brandon Schmandt Steady incision of Grand Canyon at the million year timeframe: A case for mantle-driven differential uplift, *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 397 (Jul 2014): 159–173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2014.04.020>
- [36] Rocko A. Brown, Gregory B. Pasternack Hydrologic and topographic variability modulate channel change in mountain rivers, *Journal of Hydrology* 510 (Mar 2014): 551–564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2013.12.048>
- [37] Brandon Schmandt, Richard C. Aster, Dirk Scherler, Victor C. Tsai, Karl Karlstrom Multiple fluvial processes detected by riverside seismic and infrasound monitoring of a controlled flood in the Grand Canyon, *Geophysical Research Letters* 40, no.1818 (Sep 2013): 4858–4863. <https://doi.org/10.1002/grl.50953>

- [38] Wyatt F. Cross, Colden V. Baxter, Emma J. Rosi-Marshall, Robert O. Hall, Theodore A. Kennedy, Kevin C. Donner, Holly A. Wellard Kelly, Sarah E. Z. Seegert, Kathrine E. Behn, Michael D. Yard Food-web dynamics in a large river discontinuum, *Ecological Monographs* 83, no.33 (Aug 2013): 311–337. <https://doi.org/10.1890/12-1727.1>
- [39] Yo Matsubara, Alan D. Howard, J. Parker Gochenour Hydrology of early Mars: Valley network incision, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets* 118, no.66 (Jun 2013): 1365–1387. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jgre.20081>
- [40] Paul E. Grams, David J. Topping, John C. Schmidt, Joseph E. Hazel, Matt Kaplinski Linking morphodynamic response with sediment mass balance on the Colorado River in Marble Canyon: Issues of scale, geomorphic setting, and sampling design, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface* 118, no.22 (Apr 2013): 361–381. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jgrf.20050>
- [41] G. Petts, A. Gurnell 13.7 Hydrogeomorphic Effects of Reservoirs, Dams, and Diversions, (Jan 2013): 96–114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-374739-6.00345-6>
- [42] J. G. Venditti, P. A. Nelson, J. T. Minear, J. Wooster, W. E. Dietrich Alternate bar response to sediment supply termination, *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface* 117, no.F2F2 (Jun 2012). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2011JF002254>
- [43] Christopher Hackney, Paul Carling The occurrence of obtuse junction angles and changes in channel width below tributaries along the Mekong River, south-east Asia, *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 36, no.1212 (Jun 2011): 1563–1576. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.2165>
- [44] E. B. Safran, S. W. Anderson, M. Mills-Novoa, P. K. House, L. Ely Controls on large landslide distribution and implications for the geomorphic evolution of the southern interior Columbia River basin, *Geological Society of America Bulletin* 123, no.9-109-10 (Jan 2011): 1851–1862. <https://doi.org/10.1130/B30061.1>
- [45] Luke A. Avery, David L. Ward, Jane C. Marks Exercise Conditioning Decreases Downstream Movement of Pond-Reared Razorback Suckers Released Into a Stream Environment, *Western North American Naturalist* 71, no.11 (Apr 2011): 78–85. <https://doi.org/10.3398/064.071.0111>
- [46] Wyatt F. Cross, Emma J. Rosi-Marshall, Kathrine E. Behn, Theodore A. Kennedy, Robert O. Hall, A. Elizabeth Fuller, Colden V. Baxter Invasion and production of New Zealand mud snails in the Colorado River, Glen Canyon, *Biological Invasions* 12, no.99 (Jan 2010): 3033–3043. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-010-9694-y>
- [47] I. Haviv, Y. Enzel, K. X. Whipple, E. Zilberman, A. Matmon, J. Stone, K. L. Fifield Evolution of vertical knickpoints (waterfalls) with resistant caprock: Insights from numerical modeling, *Journal of Geophysical Research* 115, no.F3F3 (Aug 2010). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2008JF001187>
- [48] Christopher S. Magirl, Jeffrey W. Gartner, Graeme M. Smart, Robert H. Webb Water velocity and the nature of critical flow in large rapids on the Colorado River, Utah, *Water Resources Research* 45 no.55 (May 2009). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2009WR007731>

- [49] Ryosuke Akahori, Mark W. Schmeeckle, David J. Topping, Theodore S. Melis Erosion properties of cohesive sediments in the Colorado River in Grand Canyon, *River Research and Applications* 24, no.88 (Oct 2008): 1160–1174. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rra.1122>
- [50] Susan G. Mortenson, Peter J. Weisberg, Barbara E. Ralston Do beavers promote the invasion of non-native Tamarix in the Grand Canyon riparian zone?, *Wetlands* 28, no.33 (Sep 2008): 666–675. <https://doi.org/10.1672/07-142.1>
- [51] Kirk R. Vincent, E. D. Andrews Depositional settings of sand beaches along whitewater rivers, *River Research and Applications* 24, no.66 (Jul 2008): 771–788. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rra.1079>
- [52] John C. Schmidt, Peter R. Wilcock Metrics for assessing the downstream effects of dams, *Water Resources Research* 44, no.44 (Apr 2008). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2006WR005092>
- [53] S. M. Wiele, P. R. Wilcock, P. E. Grams Reach-averaged sediment routing model of a canyon river, *Water Resources Research* 43, no.22 (Feb 2007). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2005WR004824>
- [54] Maureen M. Berlin, Robert S. Anderson Modeling of knickpoint retreat on the Roan Plateau, western Colorado, *Journal of Geophysical Research* 112, no.F3F3 (Jun 2007). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2006JF000553>
- [55] Brian J. Yanites, Robert H. Webb, Peter G. Griffiths, Christopher S. Magirl Debris flow deposition and reworking by the Colorado River in Grand Canyon, Arizona, *Water Resources Research* 42, no.1111 (Nov 2006). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2005WR004847>
- [56] William L. Graf Downstream hydrologic and geomorphic effects of large dams on American rivers, *Geomorphology* 79, no.3-43-4 (Sep 2006): 336–360. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2006.06.022>
- [57] Joseph E. Hazel, David J. Topping, John C. Schmidt, Matt Kaplinski Influence of a dam on fine-sediment storage in a canyon river, *Journal of Geophysical Research* 111, no.F1F1 (Jan 2006). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004JF000193>
- [58] Thomas C. Hanks, Robert H. Webb Effects of tributary debris on the longitudinal profile of the Colorado River in Grand Canyon, *Journal of Geophysical Research* 111, no.F2F2 (Jan 2006). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004JF000257>
- [59] Matt D. Anders, Joel L. Pederson, Tammy M. Rittenour, Warren D. Sharp, John C. Gosse, Karl E. Karlstrom, Laura J. Crossey, Ronald J. Goble, Lisa Stockli, Guang Yang Pleistocene geomorphology and geochronology of eastern Grand Canyon: linkages of landscape components during climate changes, *Quaternary Science Reviews* 24, no.23-2423-24 (Dec 2005): 2428–2448. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2005.03.015>
- [60] Adrian M. Harvey Looking into the Grand Canyon—and finding some answers!, *Quaternary Science Reviews* 24, no.23-2423-24 (Dec 2005): 2426–2427. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2005.08.003>

- [61] William L. Graf Geomorphology and American dams: The scientific, social, and economic context, *Geomorphology* 71, no.1-21-2 (Oct 2005): 3–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2004.05.005>
- [62] Michael D. Yard, Glenn E. Bennett, Steve N. Mietz, Lewis G. Coggins, Lawrence E. Stevens, Susan Hueftle, Dean W. Blinn Influence of topographic complexity on solar insolation estimates for the Colorado River, Grand Canyon, AZ, *Ecological Modelling* 183, no.2-32-3 (Apr 2005): 157–172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2004.07.027>
- [63] Fabio Rossano Dario, Maria Cristina Veiga De Vincenzo. Scientific and touristic expedition to the meeting the natural beauties in Arizona, U.S. *The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin* 15 (2022) 1-56

Photo 1. Flying across the Atlantic

Photo 2. Flying across the Atlantic

Photo 3. Flying across the Atlantic

Photo 4. Flying across the Atlantic

Photo 5. Flying across the Atlantic

Photo 6. Flying across the Atlantic

Photo 7. Flying across the Atlantic

Photo 8. Flying across the Atlantic

Photo 9. View of New York from the plane.

Photo 10. View of New York from the plane.

Photo 11. View of New York from the plane.

Photo 12. View of New York from the plane.

Photo 13. View of New York from the plane.

Photo 14. View of New York from the plane.

Photo 15. View of New York from the plane.

Photo 16. View of New York from the plane.

Photo 17. View of New York from the plane.

Photo 18. View of New York from the plane.

Photo 19. New York Airport

Photo 20. Tourist attraction at the airport in New York

Photo 21. New York airport area

Photo 22. New York airport area

Photo 23. New York airport area

Photo 24. New York airport area

Photo 25. New York airport area

Photo 26. New York airport area

Photo 27. Flight from New York to Phoenix

Photo 28. Flight from New York to Phoenix

Photo 29. Phoenix (AZ) airport

Photo 30. Phoenix (AZ) airport

Photo 31. Phoenix (AZ) airport

Photo 32. Photo with a soldier in Phoenix at the airport (Author).

Photo 33. Photo with a soldier in Phoenix at the airport (Author).

Photo 34. Local limousine taxis at the airport in Phoenix.

Photo 35. Local limousine taxis at the airport in Phoenix.

Photo 36. Normal but rare hotel in Phoenix.

Photo 37. Normal but rare hotel in Phoenix.

Photo 38. Normal but rare hotel in Phoenix.

Photo 39. Normal but rare hotel in Phoenix.

Photo 40. Normal but rare hotel in Phoenix.

Photo 41. Taxi trip from Phoenix to the Grand Canyon of the Colorado River.

Photo 42. Taxi trip from Phoenix to the Grand Canyon of the Colorado River.

Photo 43. Taxi trip from Phoenix to the Grand Canyon of the Colorado River.

Photo 44. Taxi trip from Phoenix to the Grand Canyon of the Colorado River.

Photo 45. Taxi trip from Phoenix to the Grand Canyon of the Colorado River.

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Photo 77. Taxi trip from Phoenix to the Grand Canyon of the Colorado River.

Photo 78. The Grand Canyon of the Colorado River.

Photo 79. The Grand Canyon of the Colorado River.

Photo 80. The Grand Canyon of the Colorado River.

Photo 81. The Grand Canyon of the Colorado River.

Photo 82. The Grand Canyon of the Colorado River (Author).

Photo 83. The Grand Canyon of the Colorado River.

Photo 84. The Grand Canyon of the Colorado River.

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Photo 97. The Grand Canyon of the Colorado River.

Photo 98. The Grand Canyon of the Colorado River (Author).

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Photo 102. The Grand Canyon of the Colorado River.

Photo 103. The Grand Canyon of the Colorado River.

Photo 104. The Grand Canyon of the Colorado River (Author).

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Photo 159. German flag hanging upside down at the hotel

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Photos 174. City of Phoenix

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Photos 177. City of Phoenix (Author).

Photos 178. City of Phoenix (Author).

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Photos 181. City of Phoenix

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Photo 195. Police car of the famous Chicago police.